

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ASYNCHRONOUS PROGRAMMING TECHNIQUES AND THEIR IMPACT ON USER EXPERIENCE IN MODERN WEB APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

This article reviews key asynchronous programming techniques and methods. It analyzes their application to improve the performance and responsiveness of web applications. It focuses on their role in providing a smooth user experience in applications with high real-time and parallel requirements. It also discusses real-world examples of how asynchronous methods are used in companies, allowing for a better understanding of their importance in creating scalable and efficient web development solutions.

Keywords: asynchronous programming, web development, UX, user experience, application performance, asynchronous methods, microservices, async/await, callbacks, promises.

Introduction

Providing a seamless and responsive user experience (UX) has become a significant task to the success of applications. One of the key techniques enabling this is asynchronous programming (AP). This method allows tasks such as server requests, file uploads, and data processing to be executed without blocking the main thread. It enables users to continue interacting with the application while background tasks are completed.

At the core of AP lies the ability to handle long-running operations without causing the user interface (UI) to freeze or slow down. Traditional synchronous programming models force the application to wait for a task to finish before proceeding, leading to potential performance bottlenecks and frustrating delays for users. In contrast, asynchronous methods allow multiple operations to run concurrently, leading to faster response times and improved overall application fluidity. The aim of this paper – to explore the various AP techniques employed in modern web development and analyze their impact on the UX.

Main part. Analysis of AP techniques in modern web applications

The implementation of AP has become a fundamental approach in modern web development, enabling the creation of responsive and user-friendly applications. With the rise of dynamic web interfaces and increasing demands for real-time interaction, it is crucial to handle tasks such as data retrieval, server communication, and file uploads without blocking the main execution thread. The effectiveness of AP is demonstrated by research on the design of the Saga coordinator, which showed that implementing AP can reduce the Saga's execution time by up to 9,74 times and increase CPU utilization to as much as 88% [1]. Different AP techniques have become foundational tools for developers, allowing more efficient handling of data fetching, API interactions. These techniques are important

for creating a responsive UX, which is especially significant in areas like finance, ride-hailing, and more, where real-time data processing and quick interactions may be valuable to user satisfaction and system performance [2].

Callbacks are one of the earliest and most widely used mechanisms for handling asynchronous operations in web development. It is a function passed as an argument to another function, to be executed once an asynchronous task is completed. This approach enables developers to define what should happen after a time-consuming operation (such as fetching data from an API) is finished, without freezing the UI.

While callbacks provide a way to handle asynchronous tasks, they can lead to complex and hard-to-maintain code when multiple operations are chained together [3]. This issue, known as «callback hell», can decrease the maintainability of an application and increase the likelihood of bugs. From a UX perspective, callbacks allow for non-blocking interactions, such as loading indicators while data is being fetched or continuing user interactions in other parts of the application. However, poorly structured callbacks can slow down application performance if not handled properly [4].

To overcome the drawbacks of callbacks, the concept of another method was introduced. A **promise** represents the eventual completion (or failure) of an asynchronous operation and allows developers to handle the result once it becomes available. Instead of passing callback functions, this approach uses the `.then()` and `catch()` methods to handle success or failure scenarios, making the code more readable and manageable. Promises are used in many programming languages, such as JavaScript (native support) and Python (via libraries like `'asyncio'`). Surveys show how such functions are beginning to be adopted by developers in AP fields (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Most implemented Async features amongst worldwide developers in 2023, % [5]

Promises greatly improve code readability and the ability to handle complex chains of asynchronous operations. This method also reduces the likelihood of «callback hell» and make it easier to manage multiple asynchronous tasks concurrently. From a UX perspective, promises enhance the performance of applications by allowing for better error handling and smoother transitions between asynchronous tasks. When a user submits a form and waits for a response from the server, promises enable the application to show appropriate feedback (e.g., a loading spinner or error message) without blocking other parts of the interface.

Web Workers provide a way to run JavaScript code in the background, allowing heavy computational tasks to be processed in a separate thread. This prevents the main UI thread from being blocked, ensuring that

the interface remains responsive even when performing resource-intensive tasks. By offloading CPU-heavy tasks like image processing, data parsing, or computations to Web Workers, developers can ensure that the UI remains smooth and responsive. This contributes to a better UX, as clients don't experience lags or interface freezes during such operations.

The introduction of **'async/await'** brought a significant improvement to AP in JavaScript. This technique builds on top of promises but provides a more concise and synchronous-looking syntax for handling asynchronous operations. An 'async' function always returns a promise, and within such a function, the 'await' keyword can be used to pause execution until the promise is resolved or rejected (fig. 2).

```

1  async function f() {
2
3      let promise = new Promise((resolve, reject) => {
4          setTimeout(() => resolve("done!"), 1000)
5      });
6
7      let result = await promise; // wait until the promise resolves (*)
8
9      alert(result); // "done!"
10 }
11
12 f();

```

Figure 2. An example of 'await' syntax in JavaScript [6]

The technique simplifies the structure of asynchronous code, making it easier to read and maintain, especially when handling multiple asynchronous tasks sequentially. This has a positive effect on UX, as developers can focus more on enhancing UI responsiveness and less on managing complex code structures. By ensuring smoother data loading processes and avoiding abrupt interface freezes, 'async/await' helps create fluid, intuitive interactions. Users can browse and add items to their cart while background processes (such as updating inventory or calculating shipping) are handled asynchronously without blocking other actions.

Coroutines are an advanced AP method available in languages like Python, Kotlin, and C++. Coroutines allow functions to pause execution (with 'yield' or

'await') and resume later, making them ideal for managing asynchronous flows that involve multiple, long-running tasks. They are similar to generators in JavaScript, but coroutines are more versatile and allow for suspending and resuming the entire function stack. Coroutines ensure that even when complex, long-running tasks are performed, such as file uploads or real-time processing, the UI remains interactive. By preventing blocking operations, they significantly enhance the fluidity and responsiveness of applications, particularly when handling multiple parallel tasks.

Reactive programming is an AP paradigm that deals with streams of data and events. Libraries like RxJS (Reactive Extensions for JavaScript) allow developers to create and manage event streams, reacting to

changes in data over time. This approach is especially useful in web applications that require real-time interaction, such as chat applications, stock price updates, or live data feeds.

This method ensures that applications can handle real-time data streams efficiently. For example, users

can see price changes without needing to reload the page. By leveraging reactive programming, developers can build highly dynamic UI that provide instant feedback, improving overall user engagement. Characteristics of the impact on UX of some of the listed AP methods are presented in table 1

Table 1.

Impact of different AP techniques on UX and their use cases

Method	Impact on UX	Use case
Callbacks	Non-blocking, but can lead to complex and hard-to-maintain code.	Handling simple async tasks, user interactions.
Promises	Improved readability, better error handling; enhances responsiveness of UI.	API requests, data fetching.
Async/Await	Simplifies code, makes it more maintainable; allows smooth handling of complex async flows.	Data fetching, sequential async operations.
Web workers	Prevents UI freezes during CPU-intensive operations; ensures UI responsiveness	Background tasks, CPU-heavy computations

Asynchronous-based methods, including callbacks, promises, and async/await, are essential for building responsive, user-friendly web applications. By handling long-running tasks in the background, these techniques minimize interface freezes and improve overall performance. While each method offers different advantages, the adoption of promises and async/await has streamlined the development process, reduced complexity and improving error handling. These approaches significantly enhance the UX, ensuring that modern web applications remain fast, responsive, and intuitive. In context of AP implementation, developers must also consider data security and sensitivity in, which are becoming increasingly crucial in today's world [7, 8].

The implementation of AP methods in a company to improve UX

Method of AP has become an important approach for companies looking to enhance UX in their web and mobile applications. By allowing applications to handle multiple tasks simultaneously without blocking the UI, different asynchronous techniques such as async/await or promises ensure seamless, real-time interactions.

One of the largest online marketplaces for short-term rentals **Airbnb** utilizes AP to provide users with a smooth and responsive experience when searching for properties. When a client searches for a location, Airbnb fetches result asynchronously, updating the UI in real time as new listings become available. This prevents the application from freezing while waiting for data from the server, ensuring that users can continue interacting with filters, maps, and other options. In addition to property searches, Airbnb uses asynchronous APIs to manage features like booking confirmations, user reviews, and availability checks, all without blocking the user's ability to navigate the platform [9].

A leader in cloud computing **Amazon Web Services (AWS)** uses AP extensively to enhance the performance and scalability of its cloud services. AWS utilizes non-blocking APIs to handle tasks like launching EC2 instances or invoking Lambda functions without making the user wait for each task to complete. Instead, these operations are processed asynchronously, allowing users to issue multiple commands simultaneously.

AWS provides an asynchronous SDK that supports non-blocking I/O through futures and async handlers, allowing developers to trigger long-running processes and return immediately while the task is processed in the background [10].

A widely-used project management tool by **Atlassian Trello** leverages AP to create a seamless and dynamic UX for task and project tracking. The platform allows users to manage tasks, move cards, and collaborate on boards in real-time. This responsiveness is achieved through a combination of WebSockets and asynchronous requests that enable updates to be handled in the background without blocking user interactions. WebSockets maintain a persistent connection between the client and server, ensuring that updates are instantly pushed to all users working on that board. Asynchronous APIs manage tasks like fetching board data, syncing changes, and updating UI without reloading the page [11].

These examples highlight the significant role AP plays in delivering fast, dynamic, and interactive UX in modern web applications. Each of these companies leverages asynchronous techniques to ensure high responsiveness and user engagement across their platforms.

Conclusion

The implementation of AP enables applications to handle tasks such as data fetching, file uploads, and real-time updates without blocking the UI. By leveraging techniques like callbacks, promises, async/await, and coroutines, developers can build highly responsive and performant applications across different programming languages. These techniques not only improve the UX by minimizing delays and ensuring smooth interactions but also make applications more scalable and efficient in handling multiple concurrent tasks. Examples from companies like Amazon, Airbnb, and Trello demonstrate the important role AP plays in delivering real-time functionality and enhancing user engagement.

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